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Introductory Engineering Physics as Learning Environment for Engineering Skills

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ABSTRACT

Successful engineering profession requires substance skills in natural sciences and engineering but substance skills only are not enough. It is recognized that successful engineering professional needs a large variety of other professional skills like critical thinking, communication skills, problem-solving skills and interpersonal skills. Skills grow from students' learning environments and their methods to study.

By tuning the methodology in introductory engineering physics theory and laboratory courses, they can be tuned towards learning environment of these skills that future professional engineers need in their professional life, not forgetting physics. Overall, the use of active engagement learning methods enhance the adaptation of the skills.

The paper presents a short review of engineering professional skills, needed for success in working life today and in the future. The paper also presents shortly a development process of elementary physics courses (theory and lab) towards an active engagement of students.

It is also important that students recognize the skills and their importance of the skills they adapt. On basis of a survey, students see the importance of the skills quite similar to engineering academics and professionals. Survey also shows that important non-technical skills develop on engagement introductory physics courses.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Stereotypical profile of an engineer among large population could be characterized as highly or purely technologically oriented male whose abilities and interests are purely concentrated in technological aspects. The community of engineering educators fortunately knows that the description does not represent the truth. Nowadays a global change and a change in working-life is so rapid that the adaptation to changing surroundings and the ability to work with people with different educational and cultural backgrounds are a part of every expertise, also engineering. But still, engineer is not an engineer without strong technological and scientific background. How to equip our engineering students with both high technological skills and all other non-technical but important working-life skills? is a challenge to engineering educators.

Engineering students are at the very first steps of growing their expertise. It is also important to help them to see the importance of non-technical skills and give them a possibility to grow into the skills that they will need during their future career as engineers. Technological expertise is mostly expertise of knowing or doing. Non-technical working-life expertise is in addition to these expertise of being, that needs a proper learning environment and time to grow. Therefore it is important that engineering students have a possibility to grow into these skills from the beginning of their studies. The importance if these non-technical working-life skills may not always be crystal clear to beginning engineering students.

2 ENGINEERING SKILLS AND ACTIVE ENGAGEMENT LEARNING METHODS

2.1 Engineering skills

European EUR-ACE accreditation criteria declares program outcomes that are minimum requirements in an engineering program [1]. Learning outcomes under EUR-ACE criteria include eight categories, which are:

- Knowledge and understanding
- Engineering practice
- Engineering analysis
- Making judgements
- Engineering design
- Investigations
- Communication and team-working
- Lifelong learning

From these categories, knowledge and understanding, engineering practice, engineering analysis and engineering design are considered more as technical and scientific knowledge that form the basis of engineering. Remaining four categories, making judgements, investigations, communication and team-working with lifelong

learning include skills that are necessary among wider range of professions and areas of expertise.

European Society of Engineering Education (SEFI) has published a position paper in engineering skills in 2016 [2]. According to the position paper, engineering skills include deep technological knowledge but also beside it the ability to adapt in the changing surroundings. The adaptation means ability to work in rapidly changing world and working environments. Engineering curriculum should support this ability by including innovative, entrepreneurial and social skills. Paper also declares that engineering profession should broaden from deep technical knowledge towards critical thinking, creative thinking, reflective thinking, systems thinking, and synthesis capabilities of novel solutions. Engineering graduates should also develop a deep understanding of ethics and sustainable development. The position paper also declares that from the first cycle, engineering student has to learn how to learn, and the learning is for life. [2]

Recent survey from Ireland recognized 17 engineering skills from systematic literature review. Their importance was also ranked by academics and engineering professionals. Six most highly ranked skills by the professionals were also most mentioned in the literature survey. They were problem solving, communication, critical thinking, practical focus, self-direction and teamwork and collaboration skills. [3]

The skills mentioned above are not only limited in engineering profession. They are also more widely recognized in working-life. In 2011, Institute for the Future for the University of Phoenix Research Institute declared ten skills needed in working-life of 2020's. [4] The skills are:

- Sense making
- Social intelligence
- Novel and adaptive thinking
- Cross-cultural competency
- Computational thinking
- New-media literacy
- Transdisciplinarity
- Design mindset
- Cognitive load management
- Virtual collaboration

How to include these important skills in engineering curriculum? The most efficient way is not to arrange a lecture series of each mentioned topic but integrate the skills in teaching and learning methods of engineering education. The growth of these skills could be a part of everyday life of university community including teaching professionals. Many of skills mentioned above can be considered as skills of modern

working-life. In a teaching and learning point of view, many of these skills are somehow present in active teaching and learning methods like Peer Instruction [5], Just in Time Teaching [6] and interactive lecture demonstrations [7].

Engineering physics courses are usually in the beginning of engineering curriculum and so at the hotspot to start the development of important skills. By including the development of suitable soft skills in introductory physics theory and laboratory courses, the courses themselves may change to more attractive to students.

2.2 Methods to study introductory physics in Tampere University of Applied Sciences

Since 2010, introductory engineering physics courses have been developed towards active engagement on both, theory and laboratory courses. The origin of the development has been a feedback from students and a pressure to develop teaching and learning towards more modern teaching and learning methods in which students take more responsibility of their own learning. The development of non-technical engineering skills comes as a side-effect of pedagogical development.

The development of introductory engineering laboratory courses have included the idea of students' self-designed laboratory work that students design, implement and report themselves, not under specific worksheet or detailed instruction. During years of implementation, students have reported their self-designed laboratory works using formal written report, poster presentation [8] or video presentation [9]. The development of introductory physics laboratories also includes the development of a course "Basics of measurement and scientific reporting", which is an integrated course in physics, mathematics and communication that supports the basic skills measuring, data processing and reporting [10]. The integrated method supports the skill development as a whole, not as separate subjects. The integrated method is visualized at fig. 1

Fig. 1. A) Separate courses, B) integrated course [10]

Theory courses in Tampere UAS have also been under development process. The main direction in development has been the active engagement of students, inspired by Hake [11]. The implementation of active engagement includes following methods.

- Peer Instruction
- Continuous assessment with week exams
- Assessed group measurement assignments in theory classes
- The use of pre-lecture assignments
- Flipped classroom

The development process of the teaching and learning methods of physics theory courses have been documented in [12-14]. Overall the methods listed above include that students need to explain their own thinking to peers and actively progress with their studying during the course, not only at the final exam.

The aim of the study is to find out

- How students see the importance of non-technical engineering skills?
- How the students see non-technical engineering skills have developed in
 - Physics theory courses studied in active engagement methods
 - Physics laboratory courses using non-traditional methods

3 METHODOLOGY AND DATA GATHERING

On basis of [1] – [4], a questionnaire was built with a set of important non-technical skills. Chosen skills were problem solving skills, critical thinking, systems thinking, practical focus, synthesis of novel solutions, team working skills, creative thinking, co-operational skills, self-directional skills, sustainability, learning how to learn, communicational skills, cognitive load management, innovation skills, social skills, ethical skills, cross cultural competency and entrepreneurial skills. Students were asked their opinion of an importance of a skill on a scale 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important). They were also asked how much each skill has developed during introductory physics theory courses and laboratory courses on a scale 1 (not at all) to 5 (very much).

A link to Google Forms questionnaire was emailed to 188 first and second year bachelor level engineering students studying electrical engineering, ICT engineering or laboratory engineering during April 2019. All of these student groups had just finished their introductory physics studies with similar study methodologies but different teachers. The courses aimed only to introductory physics and laboratory skills as described before. Either students or teachers did not know that development of non-technical skills will be asked at the end of the course.

54 (29 %) of students filled the questionnaire anonymously and answers are analysed as one group. From the data, means and standard deviations are calculated.

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The averages and standard deviations of students' answers are presented in *Table 1*. In the table, skills are presented in the order of their importance among students.

Table 1. Skills, their importance and development in introductory physics

Skill	Average and standard deviation		
	Importance	Development in physics theory courses	Development in physics laboratory courses
Problem solving skills	4.76 (SD 0.37)	3.46 (SD 0.76)	3.52 (SD 0.72)
Critical thinking	4.54 (SD 0.55)	3.44 (SD 0.89)	3.44 (SD 0.91)
Systems thinking	4.51 (SD 0.56)	3.39 (SD 0.76)	3.40 (SD 0.77)
Practical focus	4.43 (SD 0.57)	3.06 (SD 0.81)	3.06 (SD 0.82)
Synthesis of novel solutions	4.31 (SD 0.58)	3.13 (SD 0.96)	3.18 (SD 0.94)
Team working skills	4.30 (SD 0.65)	3.50 (SD 0.85)	3.48 (SD 0.85)
Creative thinking	4.28 (SD 0.62)	2.81 (SD 0.85)	2.88 (SD 0.82)
Co-operational skills	4.24 (SD 0.65)	3.31 (SD 0.88)	3.28 (SD 0.89)
Self-directional skills	4.17 (SD 0.56)	3.06 (SD 0.81)	3.06 (SD 0.82)
Sustainability	4.13 (SD 0.64)	2.46 (SD 0.85)	2.44 (SD 0.84)
Learning how to learn	4.11 (SD 0.66)	3.15 (SD 0.94)	3.14 (SD 0.94)
Communicational skills	4.02 (SD 0.47)	3.09 (SD 1.03)	3.06 (SD 1.05)
Cognitive load management	3.89 (SD 0.67)	2.57 (SD 0.85)	2.58 (SD 0.86)
Innovation skills	3.80 (SD 0.71)	2.08 (SD 0.81)	2.10 (SD 0.81)
Social skills	3.70 (SD 0.70)	2.74 (SD 0.87)	2.78 (SD .86)
Ethical skills	3.50 (SD 0.83)	1.94 (SD .77)	1.98 (SD 0.77)
Cross cultural competency	3.22 (SD 0.96)	1.61 (SD 0.75)	1.64 (SD 0.75)
Entrepreneurial skills	3.07 (SD 0.59)	1.50 (SD 0.69)	1.54 (SD 0.70)

Three most important skills scored by students were problem solving, critical thinking and systems thinking, which scored an average of over 4.5 of 5, which means that they are considered as very important. These skills were followed by practical focus, synthesis of novel solutions and team working skills. Result is quite similar to [3], in which the importance of skills were rated by academics and engineering professionals. Three of the top five skills in [3] are among six top ranked skills of students in this study. Only self-direction and communicational skills were ranked clearly less important than professionals and academics.

None of the skills' importance in questionnaire scored an average value of less than 3, which means that all skills included in the study were considered at least as neutral or important. Three less important skills were entrepreneurial skills, cross cultural competency and ethical skills, which all scored an average of 3.5 or less. So overall non-technical skills that were included in the study were considered as important or at least neutral among students.

How skills were developed during introductory physics courses? The most developed skills were problem solving skills, team working skills, critical thinking, systems thinking, co-operational skills, synthesis of novel solutions and learn how to learn. At the scale 1 (not at all) to 5 (very much), seven most developed skills scored averages between 3.14 and 3.52. This can be interpreted as the development of these skills is above average in students' opinion.

Among the top six most important skills, only practical focus was not among the most developed skills. This is a bit surprising because the practical focus was also assessed in laboratory courses.

Students were asked to assess the development between theory courses and laboratory courses separately. Averages in *Table 1* show that skill development between different types of courses are almost the same.

Three less developed skills were entrepreneurial skills, cross cultural competency and ethical skills. The skills are the same that were assessed as less important skills. The developments of these skills were assessed between 1.50 and 1.98 meaning just very little development.

As a conclusions it can be said that engineering students rank the importance of non-technical skills in a similar way to academics and engineering professionals. It is also noticeable that students see these non-technical skills developing already in the beginning of their studies in studying scientific subject that is usually felt difficult to study, if methods chosen are supporting the skill development.

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